

A Note on a Yuan Dynasty Note to a Painting from the Southern Song Period

“Sanfoqi is Jiugang and is also called Bolin”

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A scroll held by the National Palace Museum in Taipei entitled “Song Su Hanchen hua Zhao Menglei shu Wanguo chaozong tu” 宋蘇漢臣畫趙孟頫書萬國朝宗圖¹ has an interesting entry on Sanfoqi 三佛齊. Su Hanchen (1094-1172) depicted envoys attending the Song court, and Zhao Mengfu (1234-1322) several decades later² attached short descriptions of the countries which the envoys represented. The introductory phrase to Sanfoqi reads:

Sanfoqi is Jiugang and is also called Bolin (*Sānfóqí jí Jiùgǎng yòu míng Bólin* 三佛齊即舊港又名渤淋)

If one accepts the note by Zhao Mengfu as genuine and not retrospectively faked, then it constitutes knowledge of a connection between Sanfoqi, Jiugang and Bolin in the late Song and/or early Yuan period already.

The phrase appears in the following works of the Ming dynasty:

1567 (date of oldest extant print copy) Zheng Xiao 鄭曉 (1499-1566), *Wuxuebian* 吾學編 (Xuxiu Siku quanshu) *shang juan* 上卷.29b.

Ca. 1591 Luo Yuejiong 羅曰駿 (fl. 1585-1597), *Xianbin lu* 咸賓錄 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000) 6.147.

1613 Zhang Huang 章潢 (1526-1608), *Tushubian* 圖書編 (Siku quanshu), 51.27b.

1621 Mao Yuanyi 茅元儀 (1594–1640?), *Wubei zhi* 武備志 (Xuxiu Siku quanshu), “Haiwai zhuguo xu 海外諸國序”, 236.8a.

1639 Fan Jingwen 范景文 (1587-1644) *Shilü* 師律 (Xuxiu Siku quanshu), 14 *shang* 上.67b.

It is strange that if the information from Zhao Mengfu was available as early as the mid-Yuan, it was not adopted earlier than the late Ming period. The Chinese texts usually consulted on

¹ <https://digitalarchive.npm.gov.tw/>, accessed 12 June 2026. Search for 萬國朝宗圖.

² The date of Zhao Mengfu’s text reads “fourth month spring of the third year of the Yanyou era” (*Yàn yǒu sānnián chūn sìyuè* 延祐三年春四月) (1316).

early Southeast Asia do not include the phrase. Zhang Xie 張燮 (1574-1640) explains in the entry on Jiugang in the *Dong Xi yang kao* 東西洋考:

Jiugang is the Sanfoqi of old. Initially it was called Gantuoli and it was also called Bolin (*Jiùgǎng gǔ Sānfóqí yě chū míng Gāntuólì yòu míng Bólin* 舊港古三佛齊也 初名千陀利 又名渤淋)³

The only text from Ming times that I could find to echo the above information is the *Yuzhitang tanhui* 玉芝堂談薈 by Xu Yingqiu 徐應秋 (*jinshi* of 1616), but it gets the name Gantuoli wrong and does not mention Jiugang:

Sanfoqi refers to Tiantuoli and it is also called Bolin. (*Sānfóqí guó jí Tiāntuólì yòu míng Bólin* 三佛齊國 即天陀利 又名渤淋)⁴

In the description of Patani incorrectly inserted at the end of the entry on Boni in the *Ming yitong zhi* 明一統志 (1461) its location is defined as follows:

The country rules over fourteen islands. It is situated to the west of Jiugang. From Zhancheng one can reach it in forty days. Initially it was a vassal of Guawa (Zhuawa?), later it was a vassal of Xianluo. It changed its name to Dani. (*Guó tǒng shìsì zhōu zài Jiùgǎng zhī xī, zì Zhànchéng sìshí rì kě zhì. Chū shǔ Guawa, hòu shǔ Xiānlúo gǎimíng dà ní* 國統十四洲在舊港之西 自占城四十日可至 初屬瓜哇 後屬暹羅 改名大泥)⁵

The *Tushubian* (cited above) says that:

Sanfoqi is Jiugang and is also called Bolin. It is located in the sea in the southeast. Originally, it was another kind of southern *man*. It belonged initially to Guawa (Zhuawa?). Its territory consists of fifteen districts. In the east it reaches Guawa. In the southeast it extends to Manlajia (Melaka), and in the south to Dashan/large mountains. (*Sānfóqí jí Jiùgǎng yòu míng Bólin zài dōngnán hǎizhōng běn nánmán bié zhǒng chū lì Zhuawa yǒu dì shíwǔ zhōu dōng qù Zhuawa dōngnán jù Mǎnlàjiā nán jù dàshān* 三佛齊即舊港 又名淳淋 在東南海中 本南蠻別種。初隸瓜哇有地十五州 東去瓜哇 東南距滿刺加 南距大山)⁶

³ Zhang Xie, *Dong Xi yang kao*, edited and with commentaries by Xie Fang 謝方 (Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 2000), 3.59.

⁴ Xu Yingqiu, *Yuzhitang tanhui* (Siku quanshu), 10.38a.

⁵ Li Xian 李賢 (1408-1466) et al., (*Da*) *Ming yitong zhi* (大)明一統志 (Siku quanshu), 424.1b. See also Zhang Tingyu 張廷玉 (1672-1755) et al., *Mingshi* 明史 (1739; Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1974), 325.8415.

⁶ Zhang Huang, *Tushubian*, 51.27b. Yu Ruji 俞汝楫 abbreviated this detail to: 國居海中 即舊港 本南蠻別種 有地十五州. See *Libu zhi gao* 禮部志稿 (1620; Siku quanshu), 35.12b.

The editors of the *Mingshi* evidently collected material for their Sanfoqi description from various sources, and thus we find the country introduced as “Sanfoqi is the Gantuoli of old”⁷ and that once Java had overcome Sanfoqi “it changed its name to Jiugang”⁸. Furthermore, it is said to have had “control of fifteen islands (洲)”⁹ which in light of the *Tushubian* may read fifteen districts.

⁷ Zhang Tingyu et al., *Mingshi*, 324.8406.

⁸ Zhang Tingyu et al., *Mingshi*, 324.8407.

⁹ Zhang Tingyu et al., *Mingshi*, 324.8407.